

Nuclear Data Impact on Key Metrics for a Representative Molten Chloride Fast Reactor Model

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ABSTRACT

Nuclear data are an essential component of the foundation on which all modeling and simulation methods and tools are relying upon, from the front end to the back end of the nuclear fuel cycle. In this study, the impact of uncertainties in nuclear data is investigated using a representative molten chloride fast reactor model, for several important metrics, including eigenvalue, reactivity differences, and nuclide inventories. Uncertainty of k_{eff} indicates as primary driver the uncertainty in the ^{235}U (n,γ) cross section. The results obtained for the cladding temperature reactivity difference show large statistical uncertainties of over 100% in the elastic scattering sensitivities of several nuclides, which led to a large cross-section induced uncertainty. All analyses presented here used the ENDF/B-VII.1 library. Results obtained using ENDF/B-VIII.1 for k_{eff} and inventory of selected actinides indicate a significant reduction in the uncertainty as a result of the updates in the ENDF/B-VIII.1 relative to ENDF/B-VII.1.

Keywords: nuclear data impact, molten chloride fast reactor, uncertainty, nuclide inventory

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear data are an essential component of the foundation on which all modeling and simulation methods and tools are relying upon, from the front end to the back end of the nuclear fuel cycle. Assessing the impact of nuclear data on the light-water reactors (LWRs) simulations has benefited from a large diversity of resources and knowledge gathered over the past sixty years of commercial operational and experimentation. For advanced reactors however, such resources are limited [1], and related research is ongoing to investigate and address the nuclear data impacts and needs. Understanding and quantifying the impact of nuclear data and their associated uncertainties is vitally important for ensuring optimal design and safe operation of deployed advanced reactors, and for designing and safely operating the storage, transportation, and disposal systems for the used fuel that will be discharged from these reactors.

The study presented herein is part of an ongoing project funded by the US Department of Energy Office of Science Nuclear Data Program, with the aim to support the nuclear data evaluators in improving effectiveness of their tool sets and to provide resources for testing, evaluating, and validating nuclear data. The basis for nuclear data impact analysis here is a representative molten chloride fast reactor

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(MCFR) 3D model (Figure 1) that was developed [2] using simplified specifications publicly available for TeraPower's molten chloride fast reactor-demonstration (MCFR-D) plant [3]. An equivalent slice model was derived to enable computationally effective depletion calculations considering refueling with fresh fuel salt during operation [2]. The previous modeling efforts resulted in establishing an initial basis for assessing nuclear data impacts for reactor states with fresh fuel or irradiated fuel. This paper substantially extends those initial findings by presenting and discussing: top sensitivity coefficients together with top nuclide-reaction contributors to uncertainty in the effective multiplication factor k_{eff} (eigenvalue); top sensitivities and uncertainties for temperature reactivity differences; results for nuclear data-induced uncertainties in selected actinide and fission product inventories.

Figure 1. SCALE 3D full core and axial slice models

2. APPROACH

Improved versions of previous SCALE models [2] are used for performing sensitivity and uncertainty analyses in the current study. The analyses include two directions: (1) estimate the effect of the cross section uncertainties on k_{eff} and reactivity differences for the full-core and slice models, by applying SCALE computational tools [4] that are based on perturbation theory methods and (2) estimate the effect of the uncertainties in cross section and fission yield data on uncertainties in the nuclide inventory for a 5-yr irradiated fuel, using a slice model and applying a SCALE tool that is based on random sampling methods. Simulations were performed using ENDF/B-VII.1 and ENDF/B-VIII.1 libraries.

2.1. Uncertainties in eigenvalue and reactivity differences

Uncertainties in eigenvalue and reactivity differences are determined using the TSUNAMI tool set in SCALE 7.0beta with ENDF/B-VII.1 cross section and covariance libraries. Results obtained with ENDF/B-VIII.1 are also included for k_{eff} . The TSUNAMI-based analysis includes determination of energy-dependent sensitivity coefficients through first-order perturbation theory for a response of interest (e.g. eigenvalue) for all nuclides and reactions present in the used cross section library. The resulting energy-dependent sensitivity data file (SDF), along with the used cross section covariance data, are applied for subsequent computation of the uncertainty in the response of interest, based on first order error propagation. Sensitivities for a reactivity difference [5] are computed using two sets of eigenvalue sensitivity coefficients: one set corresponding to a nominal (reference) state and one corresponding to a perturbed state (one parameter is changed, i.e., fuel temperature) of the considered model.

The TSUNAMI tool set includes several neutron transport codes and sensitivity methods for calculation of sensitivity coefficients. In this study, the Shift Monte Carlo code with continuous energy cross sections is used as transport solver, in conjunction with the Iterated Fission Probability (IFP) sensitivity

approach. All Monte Carlo calculations are performed for 1000 active and 200 inactive generations, with 100,000 neutrons per generation, and 10 latent generations considered with the IFP method.

Sensitivities and uncertainties are determined for the reactivity differences resulting from the change in the following parameters of the considered MCFR-D model: (1) fuel (NaCl-UCl₃ salt) temperature; (2) cladding (Inconel alloy 625) temperature; and (3) reflector (MgO) temperature. For a perturbed state of the model, the temperature is changed relative to the nominal model, while all model parameters remained the same. The results discussed here correspond to a temperature increase of 300K relative to the nominal value for each of the three cases considered.

2.2. Uncertainties in nuclide inventory

Uncertainties in the nuclide inventory are determined using the Sampler uncertainty quantification tool in SCALE [4]. Sampler performs general uncertainty analysis for SCALE sequences by statistically sampling the input data and analyzing the output distributions for specified responses. The input parameters sampled in this case are multigroup nuclear data, and the response of interest is the nuclide inventory in the fuel salt after 5-year irradiation. Multigroup perturbation factors for cross sections, precomputed by sampling from the covariance matrix, along with perturbation factors for fission product yields, precomputed at three energy values by sampling the covariances for the independent yield uncertainties, are all available as data files and read when running Sampler with depletion models. Two nuclear data libraries were considered for Sampler simulations in this study, ENDF/B-VII.1 and ENDF/B-VIII.1.

Sampler provides several statistical post processing options to analyze the significance of the calculated uncertainties in the responses, including the squared multiple correlation index, R^2 , which ranges from 0 to 1, and which can be applied for ranking the importance of nuclide reactions to the calculated uncertainty in the response of interest. In this study, the R^2 serves in identifying which nuclides-reactions are the top contributors in the cross-section induced uncertainties for nuclide inventories.

The depletion model considered here under the Sampler sequence is a 1D TRITON model of the slice illustrated in Figure 1. This is consistent with previous efforts [2] to develop a computationally effective depletion model with constant fuel feed for a 5-year assumed operation time, to serve as a basis for nuclear data impact studies. The uranium enrichment for the initial, fresh fuel state, is 14.725 wt% (or 14.88 atom%) ²³⁵U, and the enrichment for the continuous feed is 19.75 wt% ²³⁵U. The 302-group cross section library available in SCALE to enable analyses of fast spectrum systems is used with the 1D transport solver under TRITON.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Eigenvalue: sensitivities and uncertainties

The uncertainties in eigenvalue that result from uncertainties in the ENDF/B-VII.1 cross sections are presented in Table I for the 3D full core and axial slice models, and for two fuel states in each of the models: fresh fuel and 5-yr irradiated fuel. Results obtained with ENDF/B-VIII.1 for the fresh fuel models are also included. The k_{eff} uncertainty is shown in %, along with its associated statistical uncertainty. As mentioned in Section 2.1, the sensitivities and uncertainties for k_{eff} and related reactivity differences were computed with TSUNAMI using the Monte Carlo Shift code as neutron transport solver. The positive and negative sensitivity coefficients that have absolute values greater than 0.01, for the full core model simulated using ENDF/B-VII.1 data, and for fresh fuel and 5-yr irradiated fuel, are illustrated in Figure 2. This figure also show the top contributors (with >0.1%) to the k_{eff} uncertainty for the full core model with fresh fuel, as obtained using ENDF/B-VII.1 and ENDF/B-VIII.1 libraries. The error bars shown in red color represent the statistical uncertainties for the plotted values.

Table I. k_{eff} relative uncertainty [%] for the MCFR-D models.

Model	Fresh fuel (VII.1)	Irradiated fuel (VII.1)	Fresh fuel (VIII.1)
Full core	1.7940 ± 0.0027	1.7119 ± 0.0024	0.8187 ± 0.0004
Axial slice	1.8920 ± 0.0026	1.7956 ± 0.0024	0.8302 ± 0.0003

 Figure 2. k_{eff} sensitivities and uncertainties for the core model with fresh and 5-yr irradiated fuel.

There is a significant overlap between the results obtained using ENDF/B-VII.1 for the fresh fuel and the irradiated fuel core models, with respect to which nuclide-reactions have the largest absolute values of the sensitivity coefficients. The top sensitivities are not necessarily mapped with the top nuclide-reactions contributing to k_{eff} uncertainty, as expected, given the differences in the cross sections uncertainties for the involved nuclides. The k_{eff} uncertainties for the fresh and the irradiated fuel states are close, of 1.79% and 1.71%, both being significantly greater than typical values of less than 1% for LWRs [6]. The top six contributing nuclide-reactions to the uncertainty are the same for the two considered fuel states. These results are consistent with those previously reported for the fresh fuel models [2]. However, it should be noted that the uncertainty for the irradiated fuel core model in [2] was accidentally labeled as corresponding to a depletion scenario with a continuous fresh fuel feed, but it actually corresponds to depletion with no feed; therefore, that uncertainty value is expected to differ from the data presented herein. The major contributor to k_{eff} uncertainty obtained with ENDF/B-VII.1 data, compared to the other nuclides and reactions shown, is the $^{235}\text{U} (n,\gamma)$ cross section. The other top contributors to uncertainty include (n,n') , (n,γ) , and $\bar{\nu}$ of ^{238}U and fission and χ of ^{235}U . The large

uncertainty of the ^{235}U (n,γ) cross section in ENDF/B-VII.1 was significantly revised in ENDF/B-VIII. This led to a significant reduction, close to 1%, in the k_{eff} uncertainty obtained using ENDF/B-VIII.1, for both the fresh fuel core and axial slice models. The results obtained for the axial slice model are generally consistent with those obtained for the corresponding full core model, indicating the adequacy of using the former, at a reduced computational cost, for nuclear data impact investigations.

3.2. Reactivity differences: sensitivities and uncertainties

The temperature reactivity differences for fuel ($\Delta\rho_{T_f}$), cladding ($\Delta\rho_{T_c}$) and reflector ($\Delta\rho_{T_r}$) and their associated statistical uncertainties in pcm ($1\text{pcm} = 10^{-5}$) are presented in Table II, along with their corresponding relative uncertainties in % that result from cross sections uncertainties. Also shown in this table are the top ten, by absolute value, sensitivity coefficients (S) and their relative statistical uncertainties in %. The top positive and negative S values and the top contributors to uncertainty are illustrated for temperature reactivity differences in Figure 3 for the fuel salt and in Figure 4 for the Inconel alloy cladding. The error bars shown in red color stand for statistical uncertainties in the plotted values. Results are shown only for the full core model with fresh fuel. They correspond to simulations using ENDF/B-VII.1 and a temperature increase of 300K in each of the three cases considered.

The results show a large negative fuel temperature reactivity difference, of over 2000pcm, with a small associated statistical uncertainty of 10pcm. The relative uncertainty of this reactivity difference that results from uncertainties in cross sections is $2.8 \pm 0.2\%$. The major contributor to this uncertainty (Figure 3) is the (n,γ) of ^{235}U ; the $^{24}\text{Mg}(n,\gamma)$, $^{58}\text{Ni}(n,\gamma)$ and elastic, $^{24}\text{Mg}(\text{elastic})$, and $^{238}\text{U}(n,n')$ are among the top five contributors to this uncertainty. The temperature reactivity difference for the reflector is positive (571 ± 11 pcm), and the uncertainty resulting from cross sections uncertainties is $5.9 \pm 1.3\%$. The top contributor to this uncertainty is $^{23}\text{Na}(\text{elastic})$; the (n,γ) of ^{235}U , ^{24}Mg , ^{25}Mg , and ^{62}Ni are among the top five contributors to this uncertainty.

A low negative value of 18pcm was calculated for the cladding temperature reactivity difference. However, its 1σ statistical uncertainty of 10pcm indicates that this reactivity could go into a positive range, with potential detrimental consequence on safety. The relative uncertainty that results from uncertainties in the cross sections is large, of 143%, and has a large associated statistical uncertainty of 42%. As illustrated in Figure 4, the dominant reaction for the top sensitivity coefficients is elastic scattering, with most of the top ten positive and top ten negative sensitivity coefficients including this reaction. The majority of these sensitivity coefficients have large statistical uncertainties. The effect of these large statistical uncertainties impacts the uncertainty for the reactivity difference. Eight of the top ten contributors to this uncertainty include elastic scattering; for four of them, ^{24}Mg , ^{23}Na , ^{238}U , and ^{37}Cl , the S values have statistical uncertainties over 100%. The detrimental consequence of large statistical uncertainties in elastic scattering sensitivities for advanced reactor reactivity analyses was previously emphasized [7], pointing out that the use of these sensitivities, when combined with nuclear data covariance matrices, may potentially result in misleading uncertainty results for reactivity differences. It was recently demonstrated [8] through a systematic comparison of widely used Monte Carlo based tools (MCNP, SCALE, Serpent) that these codes fail in adequately resolving energy-dependent coefficients and produce very different energy group-collapsed values for elastic sensitivity coefficients, highlighting the critical need to improve the Monte Carlo sensitivity analysis methods.

3.3. Uncertainties in nuclide inventory

To isolate and quantify the contribution of each data type to the overall uncertainty in fuel inventory predictions, two cases were analyzed with Sampler, by separately perturbing different nuclear data, with each case involving 1000 random samples (1000 depletion simulations): (1) cross sections; (2) fission yields. A few results are presented for selected actinides and fission products that are relevant for spent nuclear fuel applications such as criticality safety with burnup credit or decay heat, in Figure 5.

Figure 3. Fuel temperature reactivity difference for core model with fresh fuel: sensitivities and uncertainties.

Figure 4. Cladding temperature reactivity difference for core model with fresh fuel: sensitivities and uncertainties.

Table II. Reactivity differences: top ten sensitivity coefficients and their relative uncertainties.

$\Delta\rho_{T_f} = -2532 \pm 10$ pcm Uncert. [%] = 2.8 ± 0.2			$\Delta\rho_{T_c} = -18 \pm 10$ pcm Uncert. [%] = 142.7 ± 42.1			$\Delta\rho_{T_r} = 571 \pm 11$ pcm Uncert. [%] = 5.9 ± 1.3		
Reaction	S	rel.1 σ	Reaction	S	rel.1 σ	Reaction	S	rel.1 σ
$^{235}\text{U } \bar{\nu}$	0.90	2.2%	^{16}O elastic	17.5	63.5%	^{235}U fission	-0.99	9.5%
^{235}U fission	0.53	4.1%	^{23}Na elastic	-8.6	102.0%	$^{235}\text{U } \bar{\nu}$	-0.71	12.6%
^{24}Mg elastic	0.21	37.2%	^{24}Mg elastic	8.1	127.6%	^{23}Na elastic	-0.58	47.0%
^{16}O elastic	0.16	52.4%	^{37}Cl elastic	-6.5	137.0%	^{16}O elastic	0.56	63.3%
^{58}Ni elastic	-0.18	15.7%	^{58}Ni elastic	-4.7	82.7%	$^{238}\text{U } n,\gamma$	0.31	5.2%
$^{235}\text{U } n,\gamma$	-0.13	1.8%	^{25}Mg elastic	-4.7	69.3%	$^{238}\text{U } \bar{\nu}$	-0.29	10.6%
$^{24}\text{Mg } n,\gamma$	-0.13	0.5%	^{238}U elastic	-4.7	183.0%	^{37}Cl elastic	-0.28	99.4%
^{238}U fission	0.10	7.0%	^{26}Mg elastic	3.8	86.6%	^{238}U fission	-0.23	13.6%
$^{238}\text{U } \bar{\nu}$	0.10	7.2%	^{52}Cr elastic	-3.6	42.3%	$^{24}\text{Mg } n,\gamma$	-0.19	1.3%
$^{58}\text{Ni } n,\gamma$	-0.10	0.8%	$^{238}\text{U } n,n'$	3.4	87.6%	$^{238}\text{U } n,n'$	0.12	77.5%

This figure shows the relative uncertainty in nuclide concentrations when separately perturbing either the ENDF/B-VII.1 cross section or fission yield data.

Uncertainties for actinides are practically not affected by uncertainties in fission yield data, whereas, as expected, the fission yield uncertainties affect the uncertainties in predicted fission products concentrations, with the magnitude of the impact depending on the actual nuclide and its primary production channels. From the selected actinides, relative uncertainties greater than 10% were obtained for ^{234}U , ^{236}U , ^{238}Pu , ^{237}Np , ^{243}Am , ^{246}Cm and ^{244}Cm , the latter being known as relevant to decay heat and the most important neutron source in spent nuclear fuel. The primary uncertainty drivers for these mentioned actinides, estimated via the R^2 index, include the uncertainties of the $^{235}\text{U}(\chi)$, $^{235}\text{U}(n,\gamma)$, and $^{245}\text{Cm}(n,\gamma)$ cross sections. Sampler analyses (1,000 samples) were performed using ENDF/B-VIII.1 cross sections to examine the impact of changes in uncertainty data between libraries on the uncertainties in nuclide inventory. The results indicate significant reduction in the cross section-induced uncertainty when using ENDF/B-VIII.1, for ^{234}U , ^{236}U , ^{237}Np , and ^{238}Pu . This reduction, in the range of 7 to 14%, depending on the nuclide, is primarily the result of updated uncertainty data in ENDF/B-VIII.1, relative to ENDF/B-VII.1, for $^{235}\text{U}(\chi)$ and $^{235}\text{U}(n,\gamma)$.

Cross section uncertainties are major drivers for the inventories of the shown fission products, except for ^{109}Ag . The largest fission yield-induced uncertainties are: 10% for ^{109}Ag and in the 2-5% range for ^{155}Eu , ^{155}Gd , and ^{157}Gd . The largest cross section-induced uncertainties are: 12.5% for ^{155}Eu and in the 5-10% range for ^{134}Cs , ^{154}Eu , and ^{155}Gd . The major driver for uncertainty of ^{134}Cs is the uncertainty in the (n,γ) cross section of its precursor ^{133}Cs , while for uncertainty of ^{155}Gd the major driver is the uncertainty in the (n,γ) cross section of its parent nuclide ^{155}Eu .

Reliable estimation of nuclear data-induced uncertainties in nuclide inventories and related fuel metrics is essential for understanding and minimizing the overall uncertainties. For spent fuel analyses for example, the uncertainties resulting from nuclear data can be greater than those resulting from uncertainties in fuel irradiation history and can vary, depending on the nuclide and the fuel metric of interest (i.e., decay heat, dose rates, spent fuel reactivity). As shown here for MCFR-D and elsewhere for other reactor and fuel types, the uncertainty obtained with ENDF/B-VII.1 for the concentration of ^{155}Gd , a key neutron absorber of importance to reactor operation and spent fuel reactivity, is significant. Notable to mention, there is no covariance data in ENDF/B-VIII.1 for the $^{155}\text{Eu}(n,\gamma)$ cross section, which negatively impacts the determination of the uncertainty for the ^{155}Gd concentration in fuel.

Figure 5. Uncertainties in nuclide inventories as result of cross section and fission yields uncertainties.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the impact of uncertainties in nuclear data is investigated for a representative molten chloride fast reactor model, for several important metrics, including eigenvalue, reactivity differences, and nuclide inventories in fuel at 5-yr irradiation. Uncertainty of k_{eff} , found to be driven by the uncertainty in the $^{235}\text{U}(n,\gamma)$ cross section, is significantly reduced when using ENDF/B-VIII.1 compared

to ENDF/B-VII.1. The results obtained for the cladding temperature reactivity difference show large statistical uncertainties of over 100% in the elastic scattering sensitivities for several nuclides, which when combined with nuclear data covariance matrices may result in a misleading uncertainty result. This indicates that currently applied methods may not be sufficiently adequate for determination of scattering sensitivities, and may consequently bias the uncertainty quantification for metrics involving differences between two states of the system, such as for temperature reactivity feedback.

Uncertainties in nuclide inventories which result from uncertainties in cross sections and/or fission yields are summarized for selected actinides and fission products. Cross section uncertainties are the major drivers for uncertainties in the majority of the considered nuclides. The magnitude of the impact depends on the considered nuclide and its primary production channels. The results presented here offer a glimpse, from an end-user perspective, on the importance of the nuclear data and their uncertainties for reliable determination of nuclide inventories. Going beyond criticality, fuel inventory analyses let us identify missing covariance data, assess the impact of uncertainty updates between libraries, and identify impacts of data that are not always considered important (fission yields, decay data). It is shown that improved cross section uncertainty data in ENDF/B-VIII.1 relative to ENDF/B-VII.1 results in significant reduction of uncertainty for selected actinides. The impact of having either large or no uncertainties in nuclear data is illustrated for the $^{155}\text{Eu}(n,\gamma)$ uncertainty, which varies significantly between libraries. This uncertainty affects the reliability of predicting the concentration of ^{155}Gd , a key neutron absorber of significant importance to reactor operation and spent nuclear fuel.

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